

ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF BACTERIA UTILIZING MICROBIALLY INDUCED CALCITE PRECIPITATION (MICP) FOR THE RECYCLING WASTE CONCRETE FINES

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Abstract

During concrete production, large quantities of carbon are released into the environment. A promising route to a more sustainable construction industry involves the use of microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP) in concrete recycling. Here, we investigated utilizing the ureolytic activity of the alkaliphilic bacterium *Sporosarcina pasteurii* DSM 33 and other strains isolated from the sand as potential candidates for MICP. Powder samples of old waste concrete fines (WCF) were mixed with urea–CaCl₂ solution, in which ureolytic bacteria can precipitate CaCO₃ crystals and support their formation in WCF. Scanning electron microscopy was used to characterize the crystals according to their properties. Thus, our results suggest that MICP-prepared WCF composites could be an effective way of recycling old concrete, thereby reducing the industry's carbon footprint.

Introduction

The continuous increase in global temperatures has led to a surge in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather phenomena such as floods, hurricanes, wildfires, and heat waves. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) overproduction contributes significantly to this – global warming, leading to various climate and societal impacts. In response to these challenges, the Paris Climate Agreement was established in 2015, requiring countries to reduce especially CO₂ emissions and achieve carbon neutrality by 2060–2080.

Nowadays, the reduction of carbon footprint is primarily accomplished through the implementation of the circular economy concept. This approach revolves around the recycling and valorization of waste materials, such as those generated in the food industry (Stiborova et al., 2020) or the construction industry (Nežerka et al., 2023a), in order to recover their value.

The construction sector is a major contributor to greenhouse gas emissions, primarily through cement production. Concrete, widely used construction materials composed of cement, aggregate, and water, poses challenges in terms of waste generation and high energy demands. Recycling waste concrete, particularly waste concrete fines (WCF), is essential for achieving a circular economy. Current recycling methods involve crushing the concrete and using recycled aggregates in various applications. However, WCF, which accounts for a significant volume of crushed concrete, faces challenges in storage and handling (Nežerka et al., 2023b). Microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP) offers a potential solution for the reuse of WCF. The biomineralization process utilizes microorganisms to precipitate minerals, including calcium carbonate. Through the application of MICP with ureolytic bacteria, effective binding of WCF particles can be achieved, resulting in crack healing and improved durability.

In this study, we employed an enrichment method to isolate unknown microbial isolates from sand which were subsequently identified. All isolates were found to be ureolytically active and involved in the precipitation of calcium carbonate crystals by utilizing urea and calcium ions. By comparing the isolate with the highest urease activity to the highly ureolytic *Sporosarcina pasteurii* DSM33, we investigated the bio cementation and binding capabilities of WCF particles. Three different types of WCFs were chosen to test their abilities in MICP. The obtained results effectively demonstrated the potential of ureolytic bacteria in promoting sustainable concrete recycling through MICP and the utilization of WCF.

Methods and materials

Isolation bacteria with ureolytic activity

The isolation of bacteria with ureolytic activity involved this protocol: 32 g of the sand specimen and 7 g of WCF (gutter) were initially treated with a solution comprising 10 ml of saline and 10 ml of biocementation (MICP) solution, followed by incubation at 28 °C for 48 hours. Next, 10 ml of MICP solution was added to the samples every 48 hours, maintaining the same incubation conditions. This process was repeated five times, resulting in five bio cementation solution additions. After the incubation, two samples were collected — a sample of mineralised material and a sample of leachate (the solution that passed through the sand). Each sample was

inoculated onto a Tryptic Soy Agar (TSA) supplemented with urea (final concentration of 20 g l⁻¹) and incubated at 28 °C for 72 hours. Visually different bacterial cultures were separated by streaking them onto separate TSA supplemented with urea. As a result, nine bacterial strains were obtained and named: U1, U2, U3, U4a, U4b, U5, U6, U7, U8 (Ux = Ureolytic + name of an isolate).

Measurement of urease activity

The evaluation of urease activity involved both qualitative and quantitative analyses.

The qualitative analysis of urease activity was performed by mixing 1 ml of the bacterial suspension (OD₆₀₀ = 5) with 4 ml of the bio cementation solution and incubating at 28 °C for 48 hours. The crystal formation was assessed visually.

In the case of quantitative analysis, the determination of urease activity involved the utilization of the phenol-hypochlorite assay. The absorbance of the samples was measured at a wavelength of 620 nm. The urease assay was conducted in the following way: the bacteria were inoculated into large vessels containing Tryptone Soya Broth (TSB) supplemented with urea (final concentration of 20 g l⁻¹) and incubated at 28 °C for 72 hours. Within this period, urease activity was measured. The urease activity was calculated using the standard curve obtained by measuring the optical density (OD) of ammonium chloride at different concentrations at 620 nm.

DNA isolation and identification of isolated bacteria

DNA isolation was performed with the InstaGene Matrix kit (Bio-rad Laboratories, Inc., USA). The resulting liquid supernatant containing the extracted DNA was stored at a temperature of -20 °C.

The identification of the isolates was based on the sequence of the marker gene (16S rRNA) and two-steps PCR. The final samples were concentrated using the Genomic DNA Clean & Concentrator kit (Zymo Research, USA). The concentration of the DNA was measured using the Nanodrop One (Thermoscientific, USA). As the concentration of the DNA after the first PCR was too low (the required quantity was 10–40 ng μl⁻¹), the second PCR was conducted. Subsequently, the accuracy of both the DNA isolation and PCR reaction was confirmed through electrophoresis. The resulting genetic material was sent to SeqMe s.r.o. for Sangers sequencing.

Preparation of the WCF samples and biomineralization process

The WCF samples, obtained as a powder from various concrete facilities, were used in the study. The initial WCF suspension was prepared the following way: 7 g of WCF was combined with 10 ml of saline and 10 ml of bacterial suspension (OD₆₀₀ = 5). The pH value of the WCF suspension was adjusted to a final value of 6.8 ± 0.2. The final WCF composites involved a specialized apparatus illustrated in Figure 1. This apparatus consisted of a plastic cup with a hole at the bottom covered with filter paper. Two pipette tips provided air access to a second cup, which was placed under the filter; the same function had a hole in the lid. The WCF suspension was added to this prepared plastic cup, allowing the bio cementation solution (containing Nutrient Broth of 3.2 g l⁻¹, urea at 20 g l⁻¹ and CaCl₂ at 2.8 g l⁻¹) to be filtered through the WCF mixture, resulting in CaCO₃ precipitation. All WCF samples were incubated at 28 °C during the whole experiment. The bio cementation solution was added every 48–72 hours for a total of 28 days. Subsequently, the WCF samples were dried for 28 days at 28 °C.

Figure 1. The filter apparatus (with WCF samples)

Results and discussion

A total of nine bacterial strains were isolated using the enrichment method with urea-containing medium. The strains were named, U1, U2, U3, U4a, U4b, U5, U6, U7, U8 (Ux = Ureolytic + name of an isolate).

After the qualitative urease activity test, an additional bacterial strain was isolated, so isolate U3 was divided into U3a and U3b. Each isolate had the specific smell of ammoniac, confirming the existence of an ureolysis process. Bacteria with ureolytic activity are commonly found in various environments. For example, in the study of Bibi et al. (2018), ureolytic bacterial strains were isolated from soil, which was collected in different locations around Doha City, Qatar. The growth of ureolytic bacteria in these samples was initially stimulated using the enrichment solution containing urea. Ureolytic strains were determined with the indicator culture medium and then isolated. In total, more than half of the isolated strains had ureolytic activity.

Additionally, our study also confirms the presence of bacteria with urease activity in building materials. The identification of the isolates is shown in Table I.

Table I.

Identification of bacterial isolates (U1–U8) with urease activity

Sample	Identification	Percent identity [%]
U1	<i>Sporosarcina</i> sp.	99.0
U2	<i>Sporosarcina jandibanonis</i> LAM9210	99.2
U3a	<i>Sporosarcina</i> sp.	98.3
U3b	<i>Sporosarcina</i> sp.	99.0
U4a	<i>Sporosarcina terrae</i> LZ2	96.5
U4b	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> IAM12118	99.1
U5	<i>Siminovitchia acidifaciens</i>	99.3
U6	<i>Sporosarcina terrae</i> LZ2	98.5
U7	<i>Sporosarcina newyorkensis</i>	98.7
U8	<i>Sporosarcina</i> sp.	98.2
-	<i>Sporosarcina pasteurii</i> DSM33	99.9

Measurement of urease activity

To validate the potential of the isolated strains of capability of the MICP process, the qualitative test for urease activity was performed. Following the incubation of the reaction mixture, all samples contained calcite (visibly and clearly detected), the qualitative test confirmed the positive urease for each isolate. The visual results of the qualitative test can be observed in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Results of qualitative test of urease activity

Following the evaluation of the MICP capabilities of the isolated strains, a quantitative urease activity test was conducted at a specific time point. The cultivation time chosen for the experiment was 72 hours, allowing the isolates to complete the exponential phase and enter their stationary phase. The phenol-hypochlorite method of measuring urease activity was taken from the research conducted by Kim and Youn (2016). The results revealed that *Sporosarcina pasteurii* DSM 33 exhibited the highest urease activity (0.62 μ kat), followed by *Sporosarcina terrae* U6 (0.35 μ kat) and *Sporosarcina jandibaonis* U2 (0.22 μ kat). For these strains, the urease activity was further evaluated at different time intervals.

Table II. presents the data, indicating that after 48 hours, *Sporosarcina jandibaonis* U2 had the highest enzymatic activity (0.219 μ kat), followed by *Sporosarcina terrae* U6 after 53 hours (0.199 μ kat), and

Sporosarcina pasteurii DSM33 after 30 hours (0.270 μ kat). In previous studies on urease activity, *S. pasteurii* also note that the cultivation time beyond 24 hours is optimal for higher enzymatic activity (Achal et al. 2009, Omoregie et al. 2017, Zhao et al. 2019). Following the urease activity test, the isolate exhibiting the highest urease activity (*S. jiandibaonis* U2) was selected for a comparative analysis of its calcium carbonate precipitation ability with the MICP of *S. pasteurii* DSM33. According to the results of the previous experiment, a cultivation time of 48 hours at 28 °C was considered optimal for both selected bacterial strains.

Table II.
Bacterial isolates with their urease activity

Sample	Identification	Urease activity [μ kat]	Time of the highest activity [h]	Urease activity [μ kat]
U1	<i>Sporosarcina</i> sp.	0.12	-	-
U2	<i>Sporosarcina jiandibaonis</i> LAM9210	0.22	48	0.219
U3a	<i>Sporosarcina</i> sp.	0.15	-	-
U3b	<i>Sporosarcina</i> sp.	0.15	-	-
U4a	<i>Sporosarcina terrae</i> LZ2	0.12	-	-
U4b	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> IAM12118	0.09	-	-
U5	<i>Siminovitchia acidifaciens</i>	0.14	-	-
U6	<i>Sporosarcina terrae</i> LZ2	0.35	53	0.199
U7	<i>Sporosarcina newyorkensis</i>	0.18	-	-
U8	<i>Sporosarcina</i> sp.	0.21	-	-
-	<i>Sporosarcina pasteurii</i> DSM33	0.62	30	0.270

Biominingeralization of WCF

The experiment with WCF lasted 28 days, which was followed by an additional 28-day period of sample drying at 28 °C. Original WCF samples are presented in Figure 3. Visually, these samples had slightly different colour; the Column WCF had the most crumbly texture, while the Gutter WCF was less crumbly textured and less homogenous, the Highway WCF fell in between the previous samples in regards to all the observed qualities. The impact of the structure of granular media (mostly soils) on the bacterial viability was discussed in a few papers.

Figure 3. Powdery WCF (Gutter, Highway, and Column from left to right).

The effectiveness of MICP greatly influenced by the initial material properties (Nain et al. 2019, Amer Algaifi et al. 2020, Metwally et al. 2020). One potential solution to address this issue is the utilization of an immobilising agent. This agent creates a porous structure that provides the space for bacterial cells and necessary substances.

Figure 4 and 5 illustrate the appearance of the dried samples on the filters at the end of the experiment. At first sight, the WCF samples mineralised by *S. jiandibaonis* U2 and *S. pasteurii* DSM33 appeared similar. The presence of calcite crystals on the sample surface indicates the occurrence of the MICP process. The mineralized samples of Highway WCF and Column WCF looked more like common concrete, while Gutter WCF was very cracked regardless of the strain.

Figure 4. The WCF samples mineralised by *S. jandibaonis* U2 (Gutter, Highway, and Column from left to right; top row — samples with 2x addition of bacteria; bottom row — only initial addition of bacteria)

Figure 5. The WCF samples mineralised by *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 (Gutter, Highway, and Column from left to right; top row — samples with 2x addition of bacteria; bottom row — only initial addition of bacteria)

The appearance of the resulting mineralised WCF samples can be observed in Figure 6. All the samples except Gutter WCF samples relatively compact. Although the Column samples were solid, they were very brittle as well. The samples of Highway WCF exhibited the highest integrity. And all of the above, we can conclude that the initial texture of the WCF should not be too powdery (Column WCF) or too nonhomogeneous (Gutter WCF).

Figure 6. The mineralised WCF samples (Gutter, Highway, and Column from left to right; top row — samples mineralised by *S. pasteurii* DSM 33; bottom row — mineralised by *S. jandibaonis* U2)

If we compare the MICP abilities of different bacteria, then the samples mineralised by *S. pasteurii* DSM 33 were visually without cracks than the samples treated by *S. jandibaonis* U2. The study by Metwally et al. (2020) reveals the benefits of bacterial concrete. Researchers were comparing the compressive strength of common concrete cubes and concrete cubes treated by *S. pasteurii*. The results showed that the compressive strength of the concrete with the addition of bacteria was higher from 11 to 79%, depending on the ratio of water and solid matter (Kadapure et al. 2017, Alonso et al. 2018).

According to SEM photos, in Figure 7 (left) the sterile sample of WCF (Highway) did not contain any significant traces of the MICP process. The small formation of crystals that can be observed in Figure 7 (in the middle) are most likely products of the carbonation of concrete. However, crystals of calcium carbonate are clearly visible in Figure 7 (right), where needle crystals are probably aragonite, while the rest of the crystal formations are calcite.

Figure 7. SEM photos of the sterile Highway WCF (left); Crystals formed by *S. jandibaonis* U2 (in the middle) and by *S. pasteurii* DSM33 (right) (magnification 10 000x)

Conclusion

Ten bacterial strains were isolated using the enrichment method with a medium containing urea. Isolated microorganisms were identified based on the sequence of the marker gene (16S rRNA) using Sanger sequencing. The results of the quantitative urease activity, measured after 72 hours of cultivation, indicated that the highest enzymatic activity was detected in strains *S. jandibaonis* U2, *S. terrae* U6 and *S. pasteurii* DSM33. The bio cementation of three different WCF types was performed using strains *S. jandibaonis* U2 and *S. pasteurii* DSM33. The selected cultivation time of bacteria was at 28 °C for 48 hours. Both strains had enough MICP activity to mineralise the WCF samples. However, the WCF samples treated by *S. pasteurii* DSM33 showed higher stability of formed composite samples. The WCF samples with two additions of the bacterial suspension did not show significant differences from the samples with one addition of the bacterial suspension. Among the three types of WCF, the most visually stable samples were made of WCF (Highway), which has an intermediate texture between powdery WCF (Column) and inhomogeneous WCF (Gutter), but mechanical properties will be tested in the next study.

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